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Valuing Affordable Housing-Issues and Options

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ABSTRACT

Housing remains central to development of individuals, communities, societies, states, nations and planet. Considered as one of three basic human necessities, shelter has occupied and shall continue to occupy critical space in defining quality of life. Besides taking care of life and liberty, shelter remains major driver of economic development besides generator of large-scale employment. With large number of industries involved in producing goods, components and services used in making housing, shelter is known for its role and importance in promoting industrialization and urbanization. Occupying largest space in cities and having largest count in the built environment, housing is known to define the personality and basic character of the cities. Providing space for the family to share and live together, housing is also viewed and valued for its connectivity with health and happiness. Mandated and valued by United Nations in its various declarations, providing housing for all remains the universal agenda of all nations. However, providing shelter for all remains the most formidable challenge and opportunity for all national governments.

Keywords: *Affordable, communities, shelter, economy, industrialization*

INTRODUCTION

Shelter always remains valuable as one of the three necessities of human living, growth and development. A house is the greatest security, which one always wishes to have, as a life-time ambition. Roof over one's head is valued for providing identity and safety against climate. Quality of housing transforms the quality of life of individuals / families and makes them more happy, healthy and productive. Globally cities offering high rates of housing satisfaction are known for productivity and quality of human living.

Housing holds numerous physical, social /economic implications for human living and is known for providing identity, security, safety & quality of life, Housing remains positively linked with overall human/national development besides ensuring enjoyment of numerous economic, social & cultural rights. Housing empowers poor; securing active participation in nation building and empowers people to perform better compared to those without Housing. Housing reduces pressure on healthcare services by senior citizens besides providing greatest security against unforeseen calamities. Housing rationalizes growth / orderly development of a city/community/society, because housing, as a sector of economy, contributes 9% to India's GDP, while employing 16% of the national workforce. Accordingly, housing is known for its multiplier effect on generating wealth and promoting economy

Housing promotes Industrialization/economy by involving more than 290 industries. Housing provides large employment opportunities to rural/urban workforce; skilled /unskilled besides making contribution to local government revenue. Housing helps Labor-Intensive domestic production by creating stimulation for Small Business. Housing promotes home-based income

opportunities, besides providing family space for interacting, playing, studying and learning.

Looking holistically, housing promotes public good by creating a healthy, vibrant and productive society. Housing is also valued for shaping any society, its quality, culture, economy while holding key to restoring personal security, self-sufficiency/ dignity. Housing has been recognized as an index of growth, development; welfare of a society. In addition, housing remains closely associated with diseases/health/hygiene, higher mortality/ morbidity rates. (WHO). Housing is valued as a space where more than 1/3 rd. of human life span is spent and during recent pandemics, Covid-19, housing provided space for working, education, healthcare. Known to have largest count, among buildings existing in city, housing is valued as the major component of planning, development, and management, besides defining personality/culture of a city. Accordingly, cities/communities develop and become socially vibrant only when needs of appropriate shelters are universally met at local level. Despite, all positivity, only 15% of the nation's globally are able to meet the shelter related needs of its communities.

HOUSING ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

A city in which only a few can afford appropriate housing, has no right to call it sustainable, qualitative and affordable. Every citizen must be vested with a right to ask for a safe and affordable space to live and grow. Housing demand is known for its distinct connotations, because it is never finite, never defined, ever changing, ever evolving and devolving due to; ever increasing human population, rapid migration, changing social fabric and migrating from joint to individual families, besides jobs /education/healthcare getting localized in few large centers. Globally,

majority of cities face biggest challenges of providing safe/adequate housing for their people, especially in cities which are growing rapidly economically and physically, because of the high cost of shelter and limited availability of space for living. Cities are fast becoming commercial entities, being viewed by majority of people, as tools for making faster and larger money. Accordingly, cities are chasing money and opportunities, without caring for human dignity and human living.

Housing remains most valuable, considering its multiple implications in defining life, liberty, dignity, quality and productivity of human living. Housing remains central to development of individuals, communities, societies, states, nations and planet. Considered as one of three basic human necessities, shelter has occupied and shall continue to occupy critical space in defining quality of life. Besides taking care of life and liberty, shelter remains major driver of economic development besides generator of large-scale employment. Cities are globally valued for quality of housing and quality of life they provide for their residents. Mandated and valued, by United Nations in its various declarations, as one of the basic human necessities of life, providing housing for all, remains the universal agenda of all nations. However, providing shelter for all, remains the most formidable challenging, gigantic and difficult task facing the governments of nations, since housing remains most cost- intensive, resource- intensive and labour- intensive activity. Even people earning steady wages get marginalized in the process of owning and renting appropriate space for living.[1]

With limited availability/supply of the housing stock, cost of renting houses remain alarmingly high – accounting for sometimes more than 50% of their monthly income. Majority of people who are engaged in servicing the cities cannot

afford to live near the communities they serve and accordingly are made to bear the high costs of commuting in terms of time and money. With lower-income, majority of households are getting priced out of urban transit-accessible neighborhoods. More people are becoming homeless or compelled to drive, until they can afford to live. These new patterns weaken community relationships, undermine community resilience, lengthen daily commutes by many kilometers, increase traffic, and raise the region's greenhouse gas emissions.[2]

Considered as a labour intensive and source intensive activity, creating affordable housing in urban sector faces greatest challenge due to non-availability of reasonable priced land, increasing cost of construction materials, rising labour cost, ever increasing Government levies, charges and fee and unregulated margins of developers/builders/contractors.

Challenges of affordable housing vary across individuals, communities, nations and geographies. Housing market remains complex, affected not merely by economic factors and prevailing market conditions but also by socio-political conditions, environmental and regulatory landscape prevailing in countries and cities. Finding solutions to affordable housing and bridging ever-widening gap between demand and supply requires a deeper and broader understanding of what constitutes affordability and the factors that impact it. Existing acute shortage of affordable housing has its genesis in; increasing costs of living, low-density zoning, low floor area ratio, inadequate/limited allocation of space for affordable housing in new projects.[3]

DEMAND & SUPPLY SIDE ISSUES

Ensuring operational efficiency and effective/efficient functioning of housing

market, requires realistic and rational strategies for appropriately addressing issues, prevailing on the supply-side while stimulating interventions on the demand-side.

- **Supply side challenges;** include and involve - smooth land sourcing at affordable price in affordable quantity with supportive regulations; upgrading property tenures for minimising illegal ownership transfer, affordable financing models, state of art design, innovative construction technologies, affordable development and operational costs, levies, fees and charges.
- **Demand side Challenges;** involving realistically and rationally determining number of beneficiaries eligible for affordable housing, range of tenure models for different demographics, provisioning appropriate access to credit, determining typologies of affordable housing.[4]

OPTIONS FOR MAKING AFFORDABLE HOUSING A REALITY

Considering holistically at the complexity and magnitude of housing problems, following options can be leveraged to overcome the challenges of affordable housing in India.[5]

- Considering housing as a local problem and not a national problem,
- Accepting Right to Shelter but not Right to Ownership of Shelter, as the basic principle of providing shelter.
- Evolving a national/state/city level agenda for ensuring adequate supply of affordable housing to meet the emerging demand of affordable housing.
- Adopting strategy of 3 Ps for affordable housing ; Provision of additional volume of housing Preservation-of existing affordable housing units; and Protection tenants, who are vulnerable to displacement, under impacts of rent increase.
- Designating a dedicated agency at local level, to deal with the issue of

providing affordable housing, empowered with adequate responsibilities, resources and manpower.

- Eliminating/disincentivizing the practice of multiple ownerships of housing.
- Defining precisely the contours of affordability and affordable housing
- Involving and partnering with communities for making addition to affordable shelter
- Bringing large stock of vacant houses into the market for renting.
- Rationalising building byelaws/zoning regulations, to create supportive framework related to construction, ownership, renting and leasing of affordable housing more effective, productive and efficient.[6]
- Involving, rationally and realistically, the private sector in creating large stock of affordable housing.
- Creating an authentic data bank for realistically assessing the demand and supply and planning for affordable housing by determining precisely number of beneficiaries at local level,
- Creating rental housing on large scale besides avoiding one solution fit approach, to all sections of beneficiaries
- Creating variety of affordable housing, depending on affordability, marital status, duration, purpose, size of family and family income.
- Empowering people and involving beneficiaries for creating shelter, by making affordable housing a community-led initiative, rather than merely a government funded programme.
- Eliminating challenges of passing affordable housing to higher strata of society
- Migrating from affordable housing to affordable living by looking at the life-cycle cost rather than merely on initial cost
- Incentivizing commercially viable affordable housing, through policies and practices, that address systemic gaps in the housing value chain,

- Making affordable housing qualitative, safe, resilient and sustainable.
- Leveraging cost-effective, material-efficient, time-efficient, environmentally supportive, and qualitative construction technologies
- Creating support and enabling environment to bring all stakeholders on same platform-including- – local, state and federal government, private sector and civil society.
- Adopting a project-based approach rather than merely looking at affordable housing
- Considering affordable housing as a volume game rather than a profit game
- Ensuring time- bound clearance /approval and completion of the projects
- Rationalising government levies, fees and charges on land, projects, housing, materials
- Rationalising requirements for housing & commercial buildings near public transit, making transit-accessible housing easier and cheaper to build.
- Rationalising planning norms and standards, development Controls - shifting from merely population base to use and population base, for minimising /optimizing the use of land in projects.[7]
- Opting for flatted development rather than plotted development, for optimizing use of available urban land for housing.
- Involving landowners as co-parceners in creating large stock of affordable housing.
- Adopting volume-based approach to designing housing rather than area-based option.
- Creating large scale affordable night shelter for accommodating short-term visitors to the city.

CONCLUSION

Looking at the multiple connotations, housing should not be merely considered as a shelter, but a foundation for human health,

happiness, identity, wealth, dignity, connectivity, safety and security. Housing needs to be valued as a basic human right and not a privilege, essential for building systems that priorities people, promote equity, and ensure community/nation well-being, besides unlocking opportunities for families, historically left behind by traditional finance and development systems. For achieving the national agenda of 'Housing for All', India needs policies, programs, grass rooted advocacy, unbiased leadership and purpose-driven and community focused organizations/individuals, capable of ensuring equitable access to home ownership, affordable housing, economic mobility and neighborhood revitalization. For making cities socially vibrant, economically productive and physically livable, there is need to create support for equity based, socially-just, attainable and thriving communities. Affordable housing should never be treated as a commodity for trading or making investments and generating wealth; but must be valued as a space and a basic essential for rational growth, equitable development, improved productivity, ensuring better health and improving happiness of human beings, communities, cities, states & nations.

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